

THE IMPORTANCE OF NATIONAL FOOD CULTURE AND THE CONCEPT OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the paremia related to food culture in English and Uzbek, and describes the concept of Gastronomic tourism and the importance of national food culture in its development with extensive examples

Introduction. Gastronomic tourism is a type of travel that aims to deepen the understanding of the culture of a particular region by tasting the cuisine and dishes typical of that region. In other words, gastronomic (culinary) tourism is a travel activity that involves getting to know the history, customs and lifestyle of a region through unique experiences related to food and drink. In this, tourists participate in activities such as tasting traditional or innovative dishes of local cuisine, food festivals, cooking classes and visits to local food producers. As the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) notes, gastronomy “is not just about food; it reflects the culture, heritage, traditions and sense of community of different peoples”, therefore gastronomic tourism is recognized as “a sector that preserves cultural heritage and unites peoples”. Thus, gastronomic tourism involves not only the consumption of delicious food, but also the feeling of harmony between language and culture, that is, understanding the symbolic meanings and values behind the dishes.

Language and culture are inseparable concepts, and this harmony is especially evident in gastronomic experiences. The names of dishes, proverbs and sayings (paremias) associated with them, as well as phraseologisms, embody the worldview, traditions and values of peoples. Therefore, it is important to study the phenomenon of gastronomic tourism from a linguistic perspective - such an approach helps tourists understand the linguistic richness and cultural semantics of local dishes. Below, first of all, linguoculturological studies related to gastronomic tourism and food in world linguistics will be analyzed, and then our approach will be described based on their results. Also, suggestions and recommendations for a deeper study of the topic will be presented, and at the end of the work, a conclusion and a list of used literature will be presented.

V. A. Maslova noted that the direction of linguoculturology in linguistics studies the relationship between language and culture, that is, the reflection of national culture in language units. Linguoculturological analysis is mainly aimed at revealing not only the lexical meaning of words and phrases in a particular national language, but also the cultural and spiritual content behind them. V. I. Karasik noted that language units - words, phrases, proverbs - are manifested

as “linguoculturema” expressing the national thinking and worldview of the people. In particular, phraseological units and proverbs reflect aspects of a people, from their lifestyle and geographical environment to their history and traditions. Phraseology occupies a special place in the study of the harmony of language and culture - the images in proverbs, sayings, phrases show the people's worldview formed over the centuries. V. As A. Maslova noted, researchers have identified specific aspects of the national mindset by considering gastronomic phraseology as part of the national worldview. Research conducted within the framework of linguoculturology allows us to study the mentality and cultural values of a nation through phraseological units. In world linguistics, there is a growing interest in the study of linguistic units related to food and gastronomy. In recent years, scientific works, monographs and articles devoted to the analysis of gastronomic lexicon and phraseology in various languages have been published. In particular, the Russian linguistic school has made a significant contribution to this - Russian scientists have conducted an in-depth study of terms and expressions related to national cuisine. L.K. Bobyrsheva, comparing phraseologisms in the Russian and Adyghe languages from a linguocultural perspective, showed national features in the conceptual models of the thinking of both peoples. I.V. Sokhan in his research analyzed food as a cultural phenomenon from a philosophical and anthropological perspective, and comparatively studied the development of cuisine and gastronomy in different societies. At the same time, E.V. Kapelyushnik, studying the concept of “culinary code” (kitchen code), showed what layer of metaphorical meanings national dishes and culinary traditions create in the language. According to the scientist, behind traditional dishes and culinary practices, myths, religious beliefs and historical experiences of nations are hidden, which are reflected in the language.

In addition, E.V. Dzyuba studied the linguocognitive categorization of plant product names - that is, the structure and classification of names of vegetables, fruits, and grains in the language and in popular thinking. A.V. Baldova analyzed the cognitive metaphor model “Imagining X as food” in the Russian language and, using more than a thousand figurative expressions, illustrated the role of food metaphors in modeling and conceptualizing the world. A number of similar scientific works show that by comparing gastronomic phraseologisms and metaphors in different languages, their common and different aspects are identified and the influence of culture on the language is revealed. For example, it has been found that terms such as “bread”, “pie”, “milk” are often found in food expressions in English and Russian, which indicates the important place of these products in the lives of both peoples. However, the values they reflect in their meaning may be different - this is formed depending on cultural differences.

Conclusion. Thus, studies conducted by world linguists have confirmed the manifestation of intercultural commonality and national identity by studying the linguistic characteristics of gastronomic units. Words and expressions related to food provide valuable information about the mentality, values, and lifestyle of each people. Therefore, in our opinion, when studying gastronomic tourism from a linguistic perspective, it is necessary to work primarily based on these existing scientific approaches and conclusions. If the linguistic approach is applied to the topic of gastronomic tourism, we will be able to determine how national culture is reflected in the names of dishes and expressions related to food.

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